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Teacher Compensation, Training and Development as Correlates of Teacher Effectiveness in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated how teacher compensation, as well as training and development, impact teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. It was guided by two objectives, research questions, and hypotheses. A correlational survey design based on a quantitative approach was used. The population included 2,831 teachers and 264 principals, totaling 3,905 participants, from which a sample of 340 was selected. Data were collected through a self-designed questionnaire validated by experts in the Department of Educational Management at Sokoto State University. A pilot study confirmed the instrument's reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.83 and 0.79. Data analysis involved using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient tested the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Results revealed a significant and positive relationship between teacher compensation, training and development, and teacher effectiveness. The study concluded that fair pay and ongoing professional development are essential for improving teacher performance and instructional quality. It recommended that educational authorities and policymakers focus on competitive salaries and regular training opportunities as key strategies for enhancing teacher effectiveness and ensuring quality education in public schools.

Keywords: teacher effectiveness, compensation, training, and development

INTRODUCTION

The success of any school depends on the availability and efficiency of its human and material resources (Onah, 2018). The human resources involve the teachers whose key function is to guide the conduct of teaching and learning processes for accomplishing the desired educational goals of the school. The effectiveness of these teachers is therefore sacrosanct in determining the extent to which learners learn the desired learning experiences for becoming functional members of the society.

The concept of teacher effectiveness revolves around the statutory curricula function that a teacher performs to enable learners achieve the set educational goals in the schools. This ultimately depends on the commitment of the principals and teachers to make judicious and adequate use of both human and materials resources, to harness them together and bring job effectiveness in conformity with the standards expected. An effective teacher does not create an image of the students but aids the students in developing their own image by comprehending their issues, making any subject engaging, managing the class, and treating them fairly. Habib (2017) contends that effective teachers' activities in the classroom, are crucial to students' successful and efficient learning. Hence, enhancing teacher effectiveness is essential for raising student accomplishment and learning.

In essence, teacher's quality and effectiveness depend on a variety of factors, including their knowledge, abilities, aptitudes, motivation, and personality traits. Habib (2017) further asserted that choosing effective teachers is critically important for a school that aims at improving the quality of students' performance. This is because, effective teachers display specific abilities and skills, including the language and communication skills, an understanding of unique needs, and subject-matter expertise in the particular courses to be taught. One of the key traits of a successful teacher is their ability to design lessons, provide time for academics, keep students engaged, use suitable instructional tactics, monitor learning, and differentiate learning for various students. Effective teacher possesses in-depth understanding of the material they teach. By doing this, they encourage a passion of learning in their kids. They are also aware of the most effective teaching and learning methods for students. Effective teachers identify the learning processes that will best support certain students in their classrooms by using their expertise of those processes. Each student's progress is continuously monitored by effective teachers. As a result, they are able to offer regular performance feedback to each and every one of their students (Habib, 2017).

Teacher training and development connotes providing a teacher with skills required to maintain and improve the current job performance. On the other hand, development entails teaching or equipping a teacher with the abilities he will need for future employment (Malik & Khan, 2016). For instance, teachers must regularly attend workshops, conferences, and seminars that are created to instruct them on the most recent trends in the teaching of respective disciplines. Training is therefore intended to help teachers develop the fundamental skills necessary for their jobs to be effective. The findings from the work of Eze (2016) confirmed that training and retraining enhances teachers' productivity to a large extent.

Similarly, Ajayi, et al., (2013) examined the impact of training and development on organizational performance using participants from some selected banks as a case study. Findings from that study revealed that there is a positive correlation between training & development and organizational performance. The findings revealed further that, organizational commitment to training and development, frequency of training and reward systems accounts for high productivity. Thus, the need to motivate dedicated and committed staff through provision of training and retraining opportunities for outstanding performance Teacher welfare is another important milestone in human resource management in formal institutions of learning. Provision of adequate welfare services to teachers is instrumental to the success of schools in achieving its objectives.

Furthermore, compensation is another human resource practice that could help to influence the teacher effectiveness of secondary school. Compensation scheme comprises the salary, promotion, house allowance, medical allowance and hazard allowance for those working in dangerous area. Compensation management is the formulation and implementation of strategies with the aim of rewarding workers fairly in accordance with the organization value and policy. Compensation could be financial or non-financial in nature. Financial compensation involves given employee monetary incentives, remuneration and bonuses among others to enable them to contribute their effort positively toward the planning and coordination of secondary school. Non-financial compensation does not involve any direct payment of money and often originate from the work itself (Idemobi, et al., 2011). Depending on a given school, the component of non-monetary compensation includes certificate of recognition and participation, job security, autonomy,

employee's empowerment, opportunity for growth, sound corporation policies and provision of comfortable working environment. Compensation is one of the major components of human resource management practices that designed to enhance teacher effectiveness.

A teacher who is promoted to a new position that requires him to take on more responsibility and do wholly new duties that are distinct from those of his previous one will go up in the organisation. However, one notices that in the majority of cases, in the education sector, simply the person's title changes, not the tasks they are allocated. Promotion is a crucial strategy for motivating teachers in the educational system (Wong, 2014).

However, Lazier (2020), pointed out that promotion is a change in an employee's position to one with greater significance and pay and is marked by increased responsibility and rank. The promotion of teachers is a global issue. Teachers in Nigeria are more likely to report stress related to their pay and chances for promotion (Kamoh, et al., 2016).

A significant turning point in managing human resources in educational institutions is the topic of teacher welfare. Schools are expected to draw students' attention to their improved performance in order to emphasize their value and excellence. Despite the fact that there are many factors that affect how well schools perform, since one of the main sources of staff motivation is welfare, providing for it is crucial to determining any school's success. It is essential to present a research study to highlight how welfare issues could be better positioned within school progress as drivers of performance in order for head teachers to manage the performance of teachers (Frances, et al., 2016). The overall wellness of employees at work and at home is taken into consideration when determining salary (Onah, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

It is a well-known fact that all schools depend on a skilled and qualified teaching workforce to achieve educational outcomes, and that their success depends on their capacity to train and keep qualified teachers. However, in recent times a significant number of teachers more especially the new entrants are leaving the teaching profession within the first five years. This problem cannot be divorced from the fact that educational system more especially secondary schools are bedevilled by so many challenges ranging from inadequate funding, political interference in teachers' welfare and condition of service, promotion without implementations, lack of adequate staff training and development opportunities, low salary, among others.

Some reports had tried to link the degree of poor performance of students in the SSCE examinations in the last five years in Sokoto State with the issue of poor teacher quality that was aggravated by several factors including the poor pay they receive from the government and irregular training and development of teachers. However, the researchers could not lay their hands on any research that investigated the reality of the assumptions. This research therefore, intended to bridge this gap so as to determine whether there is actually any relationship or connection between the teacher compensation, training and development and teacher effectiveness in the schools under the study.

Research Objectives

This research sought to find out if there is a relationship between:

1. Teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Sokoto State, Nigeria
2. Teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H01: There is no significant relationship between teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria.
- H02: There is no significant relationship between teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Sokoto State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey research design of quantitative method. The population of the study was 3905 subjects consisting of 264 principals and 2831 teachers in all the public senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 340 consisting of 29 principals and 311 Teachers which was distributed based on proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two researcher-designed questionnaires titled “Teachers Training and Development and compensation Questionnaire” (TTCQ) and “Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire” (TEQ) were used to collect data for the study. Both content and face validity of the instruments were tested. Equally, Cronbach’s Alpha was used to test the reliability of the instruments after conducting a pilot study. The reliability coefficients were found to be 0.83 and 0.79 respectively. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Statistics was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Results were analysed accordingly as follows:

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant relationship between teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary school in Sokoto state.

The result of testing this hypothesis was presented in table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between human compensation and teacher effectiveness

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	r-Cal value	P-value	Decision
1	Teacher Compensation	340	3.5382	.31531	338	.600	.000	H01 Rejected
2	Teacher Effectiveness	340	3.1940	.23834				

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 1 revealed the number of participants (n) = 340, and a Crit.-r value = .600 and P-value of .000. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level = 0.05. The P-value is greater than alpha value, .000 < 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state is rejected. Therefore, there is significant positive relationship between teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. This means that the teacher compensation is cordially related to teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. By implication, it means that teacher compensation can affect teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant relationship between teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state.

The result of testing this hypothesis was presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	r-Cal value	P-value	Decision
1	Teacher Training	340	3.3229	.47230	338	.755	.000	H01 Rejected
2	Teacher Effectiveness	340	3.1940	.23834				

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 2 revealed the number of participants (n) = 340, and a Crit.-r value = .755 and P-value of .000. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level = 0.05. The P-value is greater than alpha value, .000 < 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state is rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. This means that the teacher training and development is cordially related to teacher effectiveness. By implication, it means that teacher training and development can lead to teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The study aimed to determine the relationship among teacher compensation, training and development, and teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The first finding indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between teacher compensation and teacher effectiveness and so, teacher compensation leads to teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria. This finding is similar to the study conducted by Subroto (2015) who investigated Salary and implication of teacher performance to improve the quality of education in the elementary school of Surabaya. His study found out that compensation and salaries conducted by government influenced teacher performance and quality of education. Osibanjo, et al., (2014) also agreed that Compensation is a great determinant of any employee-employer relationship and it is a factor which binds both the employees and the employer together. Islam and Ismail (2018) opined that compensation occupies a crucial position in the management of the employees in any organization. Any organization with no attractive compensation system for its employees might not achieve effective operation and the stated goals could not be well actualized.

Finding from the second hypothesis indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between teacher training and development and teacher effectiveness and therefore, teacher training and development can lead to teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria. This finding was in line with that of Laurent and Pambas, (2019) who examined timely promotion as a motivation factor for Job performance among pre-nursery school teachers in Kenya. The study explored the role of timey promotion as the motivational factor among primary school teachers. The finding of the study revealed that the primary responsibility of teacher was to ensure children holistic development, achievement of this role solely depended on timely promotion and other motivational factors such as the involvement of teacher in decision, appreciation from educational officers and good working conditions. Also, Abeeha and Bariha (2016) contends that training has the potentials to facilitate the learning of job-related knowledge, skills and behaviour by employees. Buckle and Caple (2015) states that training can include anything from teaching employees basic reading skills to advanced courses in executive leadership. Angrist and Victor (2017) Contends that training is necessary to enable employees to perform better on their current job as well as provide them with the knowledge, skills and abilities to perform in future jobs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study it was established that teacher compensation as well as teacher training and development have significant positive relationship with teacher effectiveness. It is thus concluded that teacher compensation, training and development are essential factors that contribute to teacher effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions from this study the researcher recommends the following:

- i. Government should be able to provide adequate compensation for teachers by paying them adequate salaries and other allowances so as to improve their performance for increasing their effectiveness in public schools.
- ii. Department of Quality Assurance from State Ministry of Education should provide adequate training and development for teachers. This will help to increase teacher effectiveness.

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